

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE AND SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE IN TERMS OF WORD MEANING.

Xamrayeva Nilufar Xamidullayevna

Dotsent TSTU named after Islom Karimov

Abstract. The main part of the article Pragmatic competence is distinguished from linguistic competence by defining its scope of activity and this is "the use of language in the (co)construction of a text". It is divided into three main sections: speech, functional and design competence.

Key words. Sociolinguistic competence, strategic competence, "Sociolinguistic appropriateness", Plurilingualism cultures and linguistic and non-linguistic politeness.

Annotatsiya. Maqolaning asosiy qismi Pragmatik kompetentsiya lingvistik kompetentsiyalardan o'z faoliyat doirasini belgilash bilan ajralib turadi va bu "matnni (birga) qurishda tildan foydalanish". U uchta asosiy bo'limga bo'lingan: nutq, funktsional va dizayn kompetentsiyasi.

Kalit so'zlar. Ijtimoiy lingvistik kompetentsiya, strategik kompetentsiya, maqsadli til, madaniyatlar va lingvistik va nolingvistik xushmuomalalik.

Companion Volume with New Descriptors to Common European Framework of Reference for Languages newly issued by Council of Europe (CVND to CEFR, 2018 p. 132) reflects the above mentioned models in the chapter 1 and in respect to the term of communicative competences distinguishes: linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competence. The pragmatic competence is closely related to the sociolinguistic competence therefore the following chapter provides an overview of the pragmatic aspect.

Pragmatic competence. Pragmatic competence is distinguished from linguistic competences by the definition of its scope of activity and that is "the actual language use in (co-) construction of text". It is divided into three main subsections: discourse, functional and design competence. Discourse competence in particular deals with organization, structure and arrangement of messages.

Functional competence answers the question how is a message used for communicative function. The last one, within the frame of interactional and transactional schemata, focuses on sequencing of messages. One component of this competence is Flexibility which is in effect "use of one's repertoire and selection of appropriate selection of sociolinguistic choices". There is an association between the comprehension of interactional and transactional schemata and sociolinguistic competence and for this reason it comes under "Sociolinguistic appropriateness". (CVND for CEFR 2018, p. 140-141) Pragmatic competence relates to sociolinguistic competence in terms of the meaning of utterance in the context. It deals with understanding of the rules of language use and consists of discourse, functional and design competence. The way ideas are structured and organised it is the matter of discourse competence. Their communicative functions are summarised in functional competence and design competence represents interactional patterns and processes. Pragmatic competence is closely pertained to social dimension of a language. It can be likened to computer hardware with its software in a form of sociolinguistic competence. Leech's definition of pragmatics that describes how utterances have meanings in situations brings us back to the key concept - the meaning. It encompasses this field. (Leech, 1983, p. X) Likewise, the fact that speaker's meaning' in context may differ from 'the sentence/dictionary meaning' is relevant to pragmatics and it elicits the importance of precise formulation denoted as 'Propositional Precision'. Moreover, there are two points mentioned as summarization of theoretical approaches of pragmatics related to context and the use of speech acts. The first is the need to raise awareness of learners to specific features of speech acts. Particularly, tendency to be used in a form of 'semantic-syntactic' pattern and on habitual basis. Speech acts are implemented in a sequence of steps which prompts their application or decision whether to use them or not answering questions: when, where, how and with whom. The second point is importance of knowledge of 'interactive or sociocultural principles underlying language usage' that refer to politeness theory. (Moron et al., 2009, p. XV) Sociolinguistic competence and sociolinguistic appropriateness within CEFR.

CVND to CEFR (2018, p. 139) specifies the individual components of sociolinguistic competence in four aspects: "linguistic markers of social relations; politeness conventions; register differences; dialect and aspect." "Sociolinguistic appropriateness" consists of key concepts that are operationalized in the scale including: "using polite forms and showing awareness of politeness conventions; performing language functions in an appropriate way (at lower levels in a neutral register); socialising , following basic routines at lower levels, without requiring the interlocutor(s) behaving differently (from B2) and employing idiomatic expressions, allusive usage and humour (at C levels); recognising sociocultural cues, especially those pointing to differences, and acting accordingly; adopting an appropriate register (from B2)" CVND to CEFR (2018, p. 139) Plurilingual and pluricultural competence as complement of sociolinguistic competence.

Plurilingualism is basically process of development of the linguistic repertoire of a learner who is expected to activate, use and understand any constituent of plurilinguistic repertoire including languages, dialects or varieties. Moreover, it means to be able to open to new acquisitions including alternative forms and expressions as well as incorporating paralinguistic features (mime, gesture, facial expression, etc.) (CVND to CEFR, 2018 p. 28) As Companion volume remarks, these two competences do not even "usually go hand-in-hand" but are also complementary to sociolinguistic segment. This becomes obvious in the light of the fact that "experience of them exploits pre-existing sociolinguistic and pragmatic competences which in turn develops them further".

References:

- 1) Archer, C.M. (1986). Culture bump and beyond. In J.M. Valdes, Culture bound: bridging the cultural gap in language teaching (pp. 170-178). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- 2) Blum-Kulka, S. (1983). Interpreting and performing speech acts in a second language- a cross cultural study of Hebrew and English. In N. Wolfson & E. Judd (Eds.), Sociolinguistics and language acquisition (pp. 36-55). Rowley: Newbury

House.

3) Blum-Kulka, S., House, J., & Kasper, G., (Eds.). (1989). Cross-cultural pragmatics: requests and apologies. Norwood: Ablex.

4) Clancy, P. (1990). Acquiring communicative style in Japanese. In Scarcella, R., Anderson, E., and Krashen, S. (Eds.), Developing communicative competence in a second language (pp. 27- 40). New York: Newbury House.

5) Cohen, A.D. & Olshtain, E. (1991) Teaching speech act behavior to nonnative speakers. In M.Celce-Murcia (Ed.), Teaching English as a second or foreign language (2nd ed.) (pp. 154- 165). Boston: Heinle & Heinle.

6) Nigmatovna, Y. N. (2021). WIDE USE OF ROLE GAMES IN MODERN TEACHING METHODS. INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL, 2, 115-122.

7) Nigmatovna Y. N. (2020). Principles for effective teaching and learning foreign language. International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education. Yusupova, N. N. (2023).

8) PEDAGOGIK TA'LIM KLASTERI MUHITIDA ARALASH TA'LIMNI QO 'LLASH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Innovative Development in Educational Activities, 2(19), 224-230.

9) Xamrayeva, N. (2023). MEANING ASPECTS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH EDUCATIONAL PROVERBS. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(5), 770-773.

10) Xamrayeva, N., & Olimova, M. (2023). SOTSIOLINGVISTIKA VA DIALEKTOLOGIYA. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(6), 149-154.

11) Yusupova, N. N. (2022). Intensive Learning of English in the Pedagogical Educational Environment on the Basis of Media Technologies. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 5666-5674.

12) Yusupova, N. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limning samarali usullari va komponentlari.